

Interaction of Oxygen with (0001)Zn Surface : LEED, XPS, EELS and Theoretical Calculations[†]

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EELS and XPS studies show the presence of both adsorbed atomic and molecular oxygen at low temperatures. The nature of the oxide layer formed on the surface has been characterised by LEED, angular dependent and variable temperature EELS. A loss peak around 550 cm^{-1} is assigned to an electronic transition. Results of MS-X α calculations on oxygen adsorbed on Zn surface are also discussed.

SURFACE oxidation of zinc has been investigated by employing electron diffraction, electron spectroscopy and related techniques by several workers¹⁻⁴. It is believed that an epitaxial layer of ZnO is formed on the surface in the temperature range 300-425 K although there is some uncertainty in the nature of the surface oxide at low temperatures. Low energy electron diffraction (LEED) results of Unertl and Blakely¹ show that there is no long range order at 77 K and the oxide is either amorphous or fine-grained polycrystalline. This observation is not supported by the studies of Gainey and Hopkins⁴ on the oxidation of Zn below room temperature. According to these authors, the epitaxial oxide layer is present even at 165 K. In order to resolve this uncertainty and equally importantly to establish the nature of adsorbed oxygen on the surface, we have investigated the interaction of oxygen with (0001)Zn surface by employing low-energy electron diffraction, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS), the last technique having been used for such a study for the first time on a Zn surface. The combined use of XPS and EELS has enabled us not only to identify the oxygen species on the surface but also to assign the various spectroscopic features and determine the orientation of the surface oxygen species.

We have also carried out MS-X α calculations on oxygen adsorbed epitaxially on the topmost zinc layer; the calculations have also been performed with the oxygen not occupying the epitaxial position. This study has been of value in identifying one of the EELS features as an electronic transition.

Experimental

XPS, EELS and LEED studies were carried out using a ESCA LAB-V instrument of V.G. Scientific Ltd., U.K. as reported earlier⁵. The (0001) face of zinc was obtained by cleaving in liquid nitrogen outside the vacuum chamber. The surface was

cleaned using Ar ions (500 V), annealed at 373 K for several hours and 400 K for short periods. Vacuum inside the chamber was 5×10^{-11} Torr and a clean Zn surface did not pick up impurity on keeping at 80 K for 3 h. In EELS, half-width of the monochromatic beam varied between 64 and 80 cm^{-1} . Exposures of high purity oxygen was given inside the chamber and the spectra recorded immediately. Oxygen exposures are given in langmuirs (1 L = 10^{-6} Torr. s).

Results and Discussion

EELS, XPS and LEED investigations :

Exposure of the (0001)Zn surface to oxygen in the exposure range 1-30 L at 80 K is accompanied by the appearance of a broad peak in EELS around 564 cm^{-1} and an O(1s) signal in XPS at 530 eV (Fig. 1). On further exposure to oxygen (100-1000 L), we see characteristic EELS peak at 580 and 390 cm^{-1} , accompanied by an evolution of additional O(1s) signals at 532 (atomic oxygen) and 533.5 eV

Fig. 1. (a) Electron energy loss spectra of (0001)Zn surface exposed to oxygen at 80 K and (b) O(1s) spectra of (0001)Zn surface exposed to oxygen at 80 K.

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(molecular oxygen). The 530 eV O(1s) signal is due to the surface oxide⁶; the 530-580 cm⁻¹ peak in EELS is also likely to be associated with the oxide. The LEED⁷ spots from the hexagonal surface recorded by us at 80 K are shown in Fig. 2. Only four out of the six spots are seen as the complete LEED screen is not available for observation. The

Fig. 2. LEED patterns from (0001)Zn surface at 80 K: (a) clean surface and (b) after 30L O₂ exposure. Four out of six spots can be seen.

LEED spots decrease in intensity with oxygen exposure and after an exposure of 30 L the spots become diffuse accompanied by an increase in background intensity indicating the disordered nature of the oxide layer formed. Beyond 100 L O₂ exposure (in the region of atomic and molecular oxygen formation), the spots disappear into the background. On warming the surface to 270 K, EELS show two distinct peaks at 530 and 390 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 3); the O(1s) signal at 530 eV becomes most prominent with the disappearance of the higher binding energy peaks. The observed changes in the O(1s) features are similar to those found in the

Fig. 3. EEL spectra of (0001)Zn surface exposed to 500L O₂ at 80 K and warmed to 270 K. In the inset the difference spectrum is shown.

interaction of oxygen with transition metal surfaces⁷, where initially at 80 K one sees a weak feature due to atomic oxygen accompanied by a slow evolution of a peak at higher binding energies due to the molecular species; with increase in temperature the peaks due to molecular and atomic oxygen gradually disappear leaving the low binding energy signal due to surface oxide. In order to ascertain that the feature at 533.5 eV is indeed due to molecular O₂, we have obtained the difference spectral map of the EEL spectra at 80 and 270 K. The difference spectrum (inset to Fig. 3) shows a distinct loss peak at 630 cm⁻¹ which we assign to the O-O stretching mode of molecular O₂ on the surface. Such a low O-O stretching vibrational frequency signifies a low bond order of the order of unity or less similar to that of the oxygen species characterised on Ag and Pt surfaces. The O₂ molecule is likely to be parallelly oriented to the Zn surface.

Oxidation of the Zn surface at 300 K yields an oxide layer with an O(1s) binding energy of 530 eV in XPS for oxygen exposures above 100 L (Fig. 4). In EELS, loss features appear at 530 and 390 cm⁻¹ as in the case of oxidation at 80 K. But unlike in the low-temperature oxidation, the 530 cm⁻¹ peak is weaker than that at 390 cm⁻¹. In the LEED pattern, the clean Zn surface shows regular hexagonal spots at 300 K as shown in Fig. 5a. Two different features in the LEED pattern become apparent compared to that at 80 K (Fig. 2). Firstly, the intensities of individual diffraction spots decrease and secondly,

Fig. 4. (a) EEL spectra of (0001)Zn surface exposed to oxygen at 300 K and (b) O(1s) spectra of (0001)Zn surface exposed to oxygen at 300 K.

the intensities of electron flux between the spots become stronger. This is due to the random displacement of surface atoms caused by an increase in temperature leading to incoherent scattering of electrons⁸. On oxygen exposure no additional spots are seen; this observation is similar to that reported earlier by Unertl and Blakely¹. We attribute the LEED pattern (Fig. 5b) to be characteristic of the Zn substrate as well as the surface oxide indicating an epitaxial orientation.

Electron energy loss spectra show peaks at 390 and 530 cm⁻¹ when the surface is oxidised at room temperature. One of these losses should be due to the Zn-O vibration perpendicular to the zinc

Fig. 5. LEED patterns from (0001)Zn surface at 300 K: (a) clean surface, (b) after 100L O₂ exposure, (c) 'b' cooled to 170 K and (d) 'b' cooled to 140 K.

surface as revealed by LEED. In order to understand the origin of these losses we studied the loss features from an oxidised Zn surface at room temperature in the off-specular reflection mode. In this mode, dipolar vibrations are suppressed in preference to the non-dipolar vibrations. We show the results upto an off-specular angle of 20° in Fig. 6. As an inset to this figure we have plotted the angular variation of the intensities I_1 and I_2 of the 390 and

Fig. 6. Angular dependence of the EEL spectrum of (0001)Zn exposed to 250L O₂ at 300 K. In the inset the angular variation of the intensities (I) of the EEL peaks at 530 and 390 cm⁻¹ relative to the no loss peak (I_0) are shown.

530 cm⁻¹ features, respectively. It can be clearly seen that I_1 decreases as compared to I_2 . We therefore conclude that I_1 (390 cm⁻¹) is a result of energy loss suffered (by the incident elastic beam) from vibrations of oxygen on the on-top site since dipolar vibrations, perpendicular to the surface, are suppressed in off-specular reflection⁹. The energy losses suffered by an incident beam of electrons in the off-specular mode is due to impact scattering where no selection rule is operative¹⁰ and all normal modes of the surface complex are visible with complex angular and energy dependence. The intensity I_2 (530 cm⁻¹) does not vary to a large extent with angle and its origin cannot be ascertained from this study.

The EEL feature at 390 and 530 cm⁻¹ change with the temperature of the surface. We sought to understand the origin of these changes as well as the nature of the transition responsible for the energy loss feature around 530 cm⁻¹ by first recording the spectrum of the (0001)Zn surface covered with the oxide layer at 373 K and then cooling it progressively down to 80 K (Fig. 7). At 373 K, the 530 cm⁻¹ peak appears as a shoulder next to the 390 cm⁻¹ peak, gaining prominence on cooling; at 80 K, a

Fig. 7. Temperature dependence of the loss peaks of (0001)Zn exposed to 500L O₂. In the inset phonon gain peaks at 325 and 125 K are shown.

well-defined peak is seen at 580 cm⁻¹ (shifted from 530 cm⁻¹) but the 390 cm⁻¹ peak does not exhibit any shift. At 400 K, the shoulder nearly disappears giving the appearance of a single intense peak at 390 cm⁻¹. These changes in the two loss peaks are reversible through the range of temperatures studied. The O(1s) peak does not show much change during this temperature cycling.

Accompanying the loss peaks, on the gain side of the elastic peak, peaks of relatively weak intensities are found (inset to Fig. 7). These are phonon gain peaks accompanying the Zn-O loss peaks of

the oxidised (0001)Zn surface. We find that unlike in the case of 390 cm^{-1} loss peak, the loss peak at 550 cm^{-1} has no corresponding gain feature. This is possible if the transition is electronic in origin. Inter-band transitions in this region have been reported for (0001) face of ZnO single crystal¹¹.

The temperature dependence of the EEL features is also likely to be related to the changes in the ordered structure of the oxide surface as revealed by the LEED patterns shown in Fig. 5(c, d). From epitaxial ordering of oxygen at room temperature (Fig. 5b) the spots split on cooling. In the literature⁹, spot splitting has been associated with the formation of anti-phase domains as the adsorbate occupies different adsorption sites on the substrate. We attribute the spot splitting on the Zn-O surface to shifting of the oxygen atom from the epitaxially ordered position to form large number of anti-phase domains. On cooling below 150 K, the background intensity increases, weakening the spots further until they disappear. The complete absence of LEED spots indicates the lack of coherence scattering from the disordered Zn-O surface. The shift in the peak position of the electronic transition around 530 cm^{-1} is likely to be associated with the oxygen adsorption sites on the zinc surface. In what follows we discuss the results of MS-X α calculations on oxygen adsorbed on the (0001)Zn surface.

MS-X α calculations on oxygen adsorbed on the (0001)Zn surface :

The method : The SCF-MS-X α method is a technique used to approximate solutions to the Hartree-Fock equations for a many-electron system. The method is based on a hypothetical decomposition of matter into characteristic units (clusters) of atoms. Together with the environment (vacuum, crystal, surface) one unit is considered to represent physical situations, such as molecules in the gaseous phase, a typical atomic arrangement in a macromolecule, or a set of atoms in a bulk crystal or on a crystal surface.

The two characteristic approximations of the method are the use of the X α approximation for the exchange potential¹² and the muffin-tin approximation for the potential. In the latter approximation, the molecule is partitioned into three fundamental types of regions : atomic, inter-atomic and intra-molecular (this is the region outside the sphere which encloses the entire molecule). The potentials in the atomic and extramolecular regions are spherically averaged (by constructing a sphere of suitable radius) while a constant potential is used in the inter-atomic region. The molecular orbitals are characterised by the charge associated with each atomic sphere, and with the region outside the outer sphere, in terms of the percentage of s, p, d, etc. character and the charge in the inter-sphere region. The total charge associated with each atom in a molecule is taken to be the sum of the charge inside the atomic sphere around the atom and a fraction of the inter-sphere charge.

The latter was obtained by the inter-sphere charge partitioning scheme of Case and Karplus¹³ in which the inter-sphere charge is partitioned among the basis functions centered on the various atoms in proportion to the average charge density at the surface of each atomic sphere multiplied by the area of that bordering the inter-sphere region. Thus, the fractional s, p, d, etc. character of the contribution of each atom to the molecular orbital can be calculated. In the present study, we have carried out MS-X α calculations on two geometries of oxygen adsorbed on the (0001)Zn surface.

The cluster model used to represent the zinc surface with the oxygen atom occupying the three-fold hollow site (geometry 1) is depicted in Fig. 8. The first layer consists of three Zn atoms and the three-fold site has a Zn atom in the second layer.

Fig. 8. Cluster used for MS X α study of oxygen adsorption on (0001) Zn surface with C_{3v} symmetry.

This cluster has three-fold symmetry about the z axis and oxygen chemisorption was considered to maintain the C_{3v} symmetry. In geometry 2 (Fig. 9), the oxygen atom was placed epitaxially on a zinc atom at the centre of a hexagon formed by six zinc atoms. The Zn-O axis was taken as the z axis and the oxygen chemisorption maintained the C_{6v} symmetry. The Zn-Zn distances were obtained

Fig. 9. Cluster used for MS-X α study of oxygen adsorption on (0001)Zn surface with C_{6v} symmetry.

from their corresponding values in the bulk and the oxygen atom was fixed at a height of 2.8 a.u. (atomic units) from the topmost layer of zinc atoms. This value was reported by Miyazaki *et al.*¹³ to be the equilibrium distance for oxygen chemisorption on the (0001)Zn surface. Geometry 2 is identified with ordered oxygen on the surface while geometry 1 is due to a disordered surface (a surface not ordered according to our definition).

In the MS-X α calculations the atomic α parameters (Table 1) were those of Schwartz¹⁴ and a weighted average of the atomic α values was used in the inter-atomic and extra-molecular regions. The sphere radii were fixed according to the procedure of Norman¹⁵ allowing for overlap between the different spheres. It is well known that allowing for overlapping spheres reduces the artificial nature of the muffin-tin approximations to some extent¹⁶. We find that overlap in the range of 15-25% gives consistent results. Due to the different geometries used in the present study, the amount of Zn-Zn and Zn-O overlaps could not be fixed but were kept between 15 and 25%. The virial ratio $-2T/V$ was within the limits 1.000 ± 0.002 indicating that the choice of sphere radii was reasonably good. The outer sphere with origin at the centre of the cluster (Fig. 9b) was chosen to touch the spheres farthest from the centre.

The partial wave expansions were truncated at $l=4$ for the outer sphere, $l=2$ for zinc and $l=1$ for oxygen. The core energy levels $1s$, $2s$, $2p$, $3s$, $3p$ on zinc and $1s$ on oxygen were calculated in each iteration using only the surrounding atomic potentials. The calculations were carried out self-consistently with the convergence criterion that the maximum relative change in potential between two consecutive iterations was lower than 10^{-8} or the variation of the energy levels were not more than 0.003 eV (0.0002 Ry).

Electronic structure : The MS-X α calculation of the ground electronic state of geometry 1 predicts the highest occupied orbital to be $8e$; this is essentially metallic in character and is primarily a $3d_{xy}$ orbital on Zn(2) hybridised with the $4p$ orbital of Zn(1). This is followed by a weak bonding orbital $8a_1$ between Zn(2) and oxygen. The next few orbitals ($3a_2$ - $5e$) are primarily Zn($3d$) in character and essentially non-binding. The orbital $6a_1$ which follows this non-bonding set accounts for bonding between Zn(1), Zn(2) and the oxygen atom. The $4e$ orbital at 11.3 eV is essentially O($2p$) in character and the $5a_1$ orbital next to that contributes to bonding between Zn(1) and the oxygen atom. The $2p$ core level binding energies of Zn(1) and Zn(2) shows a higher binding energy for Zn(1) indicating a large transfer of electrons

 TABLE 1—PARAMETERS USED FOR SETTING UP MS-X α CALCULATION

	Sphere radius (a.u.)		α	Charge on the atoms	
	Geometry 1	Geometry 2		Geometry 1	Geometry 2
Zn(1)	3.148	2.090	0.70673	29.56	29.05
Zn(2)	2.689	2.879	0.70673	29.32	29.15
Oxygen	2.008	1.716	0.74447	7.57	7.27
Outer sphere	7.522	7.919	0.71092	2.67	0.20
Inter-sphere	—	—	0.71092	2.09	4.10

TABLE 2—SOME ENERGIES AND CHARGE DISTRIBUTION (%) FOR GEOMETRY 1

Orbital	Energy eV	Zn(1)			Zn(2)			O	
		d	s	p	d	s	p	s	p
$10a_1$	1.005	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
$10e$	2.740	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
$9e$	5.329	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
$9a_1$	5.386	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
$8e$	5.437	—	—	29.6	56.4	9.5	4.5	—	1.0
$8a_1$	5.499	—	—	6.0	75.1	3.1	1.1	1.0	12.4
$3a_2$	5.814	—	—	—	99.0	—	—	—	—
$7e$	5.857	—	—	2.1	92.6	—	—	—	4.8
$2a_2$	6.080	—	—	—	100	—	—	—	—
$6e$	6.529	—	—	8.5	90.3	—	—	—	—
$7a_1$	6.628	—	—	—	97.0	2.4	—	—	—
$5e$	6.858	—	—	8.8	83.1	4.0	1.3	—	2.2
$6a_1$	7.791	1.1	12.2	25.1	35.4	10.2	1.4	—	12.5
$4e$	11.928	—	—	—	3.0	1.6	1.1	—	93.0
$5a_1$	12.551	—	69.0	—	—	4.2	—	3.5	22.0
$4a_1$	25.958	—	—	—	—	1.5	—	98.7	—
$1a_2$	75.958	—	—	—	—	—	99.5	—	—
O(1s)	523.648	—	—	—	—	—	—	100	—
Zn(1) 2p	1007.420	—	—	100	—	—	—	—	—
Zn(2) 2p	998.543	—	—	—	—	—	100	—	—
Zn(1) 2s	1143.542	—	100	—	—	—	—	—	—
Zn(2) 2s	1122.571	—	—	—	—	100	—	—	—
Zn(1) 1s	9374.779	—	100	—	—	—	—	—	—
Zn(2) 1s	9372.072	—	—	—	—	100	—	—	—

Inter-sphere and outer sphere charges have been left out; these contributions are between 1 to 2%.

from this atom to oxygen as well as the surrounding Zn(2) atoms responsible for the bonding. Some energy levels and charge distributions are shown in Table 2.

In Table 3 we have listed some excitation energies for oxygen in the hollow position (geometry 1) using both the orbital energy difference and the transition state procedures^{1,2}. We see that the lowest transition energies ($8e \rightarrow 9a_1$ and $8e \rightarrow 9e$)

TABLE 3—SOME GROUND STATE ENERGIES AND EXCITATION ENERGIES FOR GEOMETRY 1*

Orbital	Energy (eV)	Excitation energy (eV)		
		Transition	Orbital energy difference	Transition state
$10a_1$	1.005	$8e \rightarrow 9a_1$	0.101	0.350
$10e$	2.740	$8e \rightarrow 9e$	0.108	0.248
$9e$	5.329	$8e \rightarrow 10e$	2.697	2.950
$9a_1$	5.336	$8e \rightarrow 10a_1$	4.432	5.670
$8e$	5.487			
$8a_1$	5.499			
$3a_2$	5.814			
$7e$	5.857			
$2a_2$	6.080			
$6e$	6.529			

* $8e$ is the highest occupied state. Orbitals have been labeled according to C_{2v} symmetry.

are 0.101 and 0.108 eV which are comparable to the electronic transition energy of 75 meV (0.075 eV) obtained by us for the low temperature disordered state of oxide on zinc by EELS. The transition state procedure, which allows for the relaxation of the energy levels gives much higher transition energies and is not suitable for such transitions in chemisorption systems indicating that relaxation does not play an important role in these systems.

We have also calculated the ground electronic state for oxygen in the on-top site shown in Fig. 9. Our EELS and LEED results indicated this orientation of the oxygen atom at the laboratory and higher temperatures. Some of the occupied and unoccupied ground state energies calculated for this cluster are listed in Table 4. We have also listed the excitation energies from the highest occupied molecular orbital $7e_2$ to the unoccupied orbitals ($8a_1$, $9a_1$, $10e_1$ and $10a_1$). This orbital being half filled, we have also listed some excitation energies arising out of transitions from the filled orbitals $9e_1$, $8e_1$ and $6e_2$ to $7e_2$. The lowest excitation energy obtained in this geometry is 0.046 eV (46 meV) which is very much lower than that obtained for oxygen in the hollow site (geometry 1). Temperature-dependence of the EELS feature at 80 K around 550 cm^{-1} ($\sim 70 \text{ meV}$) showed a gradual loss in

intensity as well as a shift to lower loss frequencies with the increase in temperature. At 400 K, this peak appears completely merged with the peak at 390 cm^{-1} (48 meV). The values obtained by us for electronic excitation from the MS-X α method are in general agreement with the values observed by EELS. We could also see that when the oxygen atom is aligned on top of the zinc atoms, the excitation energies are lower than when it is not. This is in agreement with the temperature dependence of the EELS feature around 70 meV indicating its electronic origin.

TABLE 4—SOME GROUND STATE ENERGIES AND EXCITATION ENERGIES FOR GEOMETRY 2*

Orbital	Energy (eV)	Excitation energy (eV)		
		Transition	Orbital energy difference	Transition state
$10a_1$	4.826	$7e_2 \rightarrow 8e_2$	0.046	0.152
$10e_1$	4.867	$7e_2 \rightarrow 9a_1$	0.115	0.180
$9a_1$	4.882	$7e_2 \rightarrow 10e_1$	0.130	0.251
$8e_2$	4.915	$7e_2 \rightarrow 10a_1$	0.171	0.264
$7e_2$	4.997	$9e_1 \rightarrow 7e_2$	0.059	0.152
$9e_1$	5.856	$8e_1 \rightarrow 7e_2$	0.049	0.160
$8e_1$	6.243	$6e_2 \rightarrow 7e_2$	0.055	0.100
$6e_2$	6.397			
$8a_1$	6.684			
$7a_1$	7.899			

* $7e_2$ is the highest occupied energy level. Orbitals have been labeled according to C_{2v} symmetry.

References

1. W. N. UNKERTL and J. M. BLAKELY, *Surf. Sci.*, 1977, **69**, 23.
2. C. R. BRUNDLE and R. I. BICKLEY, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 2*, 1979, 1030.
3. D. D. SARMA, M. S. HEGDE and C. N. R. RAO, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1980, **73**, 443.
4. T. C. GAINNEY and B. J. HOPKINS, *J. Phys. C*, 1981, **14**, 5763.
5. K. PRABHAKARAN, M. S. HEGDE and C. N. R. RAO, *Chem. Lett.*, 1985, **4**, 423.
6. C. T. AU and M. W. ROBERTS, *Proc. R. Soc. London, Ser. A*, 1984, **396**, 165.
7. P. V. KAMATH and C. N. R. RAO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **88**, 464.
8. J. B. PENDRY in "Low Energy Electron Diffraction", Academic Press, London, 1974.
9. H. IBACH, H. HOPSTER and B. A. SEXTON, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 1977, **1**, 1.
10. W. HO, R. F. WILLIS and E. W. PLUMMER, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 1978, **40**, 1463.
11. H. LUTH, *Surf. Sci.*, 1973, **37**, 90.
12. D. A. GASE and M. KARPLUS, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1976, **39**, 93.
13. E. MIYAZAKI, M. TSUKADA and H. ADACHI, *Surf. Sci.*, 1983, **131**, L390.
14. K. SCHWARTZ, *Phys. Rev. B*, 1972, **5**, 2466.
15. J. G. NORMAN, *Mol. Phys.*, 1976, **31**, 1191.
16. F. HERMAN, A. R. WILLIAMS and K. JOHNSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1974, **61**, 3508.